

SENIOR LIVING: THE ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABLE APPROACH

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Introduction

Aging is an inevitable and extremely complicated procedure developed in time. Aging is part of our development, as we age, we learn, and as we learn, we develop physically, mentally, socially. Stated by the British Society of Gerontology through scientific results "Aging is under environmental and genetic control but it is not programmed nor it is inevitable."¹ Thus, issues accompanying aging like the loss of bodily function were the spirit wants but the body fails to execute in bound to happen. The transition time from early adulthood to senior years is the period where the specific person's value, identity and reasons of existence is re-evaluated by him/her self or by other people. The realization of physical boundaries, endurance and fear of injury, the development of chronic illnesses along with negative emotions of losing control from the facts happening around, are all signs of aging were things are not as they used to be. During the aging process, the living needs change, the tiered body starts declining, and chronic diseases start emerging. Inhabitation, mobility, and living isolation start becoming an everyday problems and the need for assisting help a must. This is the period were seniors start recognizing the extra need for assisting in order to perform the simplest activities of everyday life. Living environment conditions as registered by KEMA organization for Cyprus seniors' turns to be one of the most important thought during the third age².

The fast track of our contemporary life makes people get apart from close relationships like the family bond and unfortunately, a parent with aging disabilities adds an extra stress to the "child's" mind for his/her parents well being. In case the "child" does not have time or even space and will to accommodate the elderly parent then two are the remaining solutions. In Cyprus, it is greatly common to hire a foreigner assistant to come and live at the seniors' house for personal and house maintenance care, was the alternative solution is the seniors reposition for temporary or permanent accommodation to an Elderly Care Facility. Senior Facilities in the Cypriots mind equals with the last resolution, the last habitat before death were in contrast seniors in foreigner countries are willing to move from their house to specially elderly designed facilities were through well thought architectural space combinations and social programs, healthy and social environment of co-existence is promoted. In order to avoid the most common emotions when one is admitted at an aged centre of exclusion, loneliness, helplessness, and boredom, the method of integration within a new framework was part of the solution in resent senior housing developments successfully aiding seniors feel part of a greater network.³

Were abroad the development of Elderly Centre is highly motivated and well process for optimum spatial and health results in Cyprus the issue of seniors living in centres still needs farther development in order to reach the level of the rest well developed countries. The lack of prober advanced facilities and maintenance of the existing structures, is an issue that needs farther attention and new solutions. The living space no matter the age of the user always has the ability to influence the users' response as Pallasmaa wrote, "The objects that surround my body reflect its possible action upon them. As a consequence of this implied action a bodily reaction is an inseparable aspect of the experience of architecture"⁴.

This paper is proposing a different type of Cypriot Senior Centres were the environmental and social conditions will be able to improve the residents quality of life, exposing them with a variety of ages and activities demonstrating how it will be beneficial on their mental and physical state. The general aim of this paper is to change the negative mentality of Cypriots towards the elderly centre by incorporating many of the results, extracted from the environmental studies, successful examples from American senior programs as well as architectural projects from Holland. The proposal will not only be based on the empowerment of the health and mental state of the resident but it will also address social issues proposing social integration programs from the new facilities to the public and vice versa.

Effects of Aging

Aging is an unavoidable physical and mental growth. In order to understand why we age and why some people age faster or more "gracefully" transition from adulthood to the senior years we need to understand how aging occurs. By briefly explaining the genes importance as well as the significance of emotions and the surrounding

environment the reader will gain a more spherical comprehension of aging through science, psychology, socialization, and design.

An important realization of increasing numbers of senior population longevity not only in foreign countries as well as in Cyprus notify the need for more attention to the problem of elderly living at the various care centres which currently lack sufficient elements subtracted from the various study results like the element of socialization. By understanding how the environment can influence this socialization as well as a variety of emotions to the user, great outcomes can occur in the Senior Care Developments in Cyprus.

Ageing within the demanding society of 21st century is not easy. The context of our aging development includes a complex network of personal relations starting from the small scale of the house, the neighbourhood and expanding to the town and the country. The environment that we grow within, family, social network, build, or non-build surroundings, shapes, and redefines every fibre of ones being differently. People have a view of his/her own image and how other people perceive them. This image is important for self-identity and is greatly influenced and empowered or weakens by social network reactions as well as the greater public. According to Prof. Thomas Kirkwood, psyche has the power to influence the physical appearance of a person greatly.⁵

As the time passes, various experiences and environmental exposure shapes the person's character. Pallasmaa introduced the notion of body image or body schema as the centre of integration. Through the years, the surrounding environment that one grew in changes and people start facing the reality of limitation where something was easy to be physically done before now is a straggle. In younger age, the mentality was completely different and the person use to feel powerful to act as pleased, the idea that nothing could prevent one from dream completion. When that person reach the age of retirement as well as when the age symptoms start appearing with a stronger impact the perspective of control and power over things is shaken. By experiencing the decrease of sense of personal power, and when the whole concept of self-control and control of the events happenings around stops to exist or is declined in a great manner, the questioning of self-worth rises and the previous self-esteem is taken aback.⁶ "Older persons who feel rejected or neglected are more likely to see their health as being poor than those who accepted...under such circumstances many of our older people are desolated, depressed, and sick"⁷. The ultimate goal for senior empowerment within the social context would be to provide facilities and programs which will promotes the ability for an elderly person to develop independent positive satisfying lifestyles a matter that will be more examined within the following parts.

What is therapeutic design?

The period of 1960s and 1970s was the time were serious studies specialized in environmental psychology appeared. Various studies in specific hospital, psychiatric and elderly centres were part of the examined environments in the quest of understanding how the surroundings have the great power to influence the users' biological as well as mental response positive or negative. George L. Engel (1913-1999) American psychiatrist, understood and promoted the notion of the aging experience as a holistic approach where the environmental factors have a great influence to the individuals' experience⁸.

The scientific and biological advancement during the early 21st century helped to even more in detail investigation were neuroscience and architecture came together under the Academy of Neuroscience for Architecture during 2003.⁹ This benefit of space comprehension like colour reading, space height, views and textures along with other spatial elements the prediction of the possible users' reaction is a great knowledge key, which offers the ability to the architect or designer to plan according to the ideal outcomes. Even though the Academy of Neuroscience for Architecture is a considerably resent foundation and the studies performed by the institute will need at least 10 years of testing to be verified, a large amount of investigations has already been completed during the previous years. Those results were based on emotional and physical reaction of the person's involvement to the tested setting like most noticing element being nature.

Healing and therapeutic attributes are part of nature. Recent studies by Terry Hartig, current Professor in Applied Psychology at Uppsala University and his associates in Sweden¹⁰ confirmed the strong effects that nature can have on people's health and sense of restoration just by walking in nature settings. Not only being in nature can actually have healing and help recovery from any physical or mental trauma but also just the view of a nature setting can have the same impact in people who lack the ability of physical movement and spent a

large amount of time in bed. This theory was tested at hospital centre on patients who had their gall bladder surgery. Half of the patients were located in a room where the room was facing nature while the other half were assigned to a room which was facing a brick wall. The patients who were allocated in the nature view rooms had less post surgical complications like nausea and headache, there negative evaluations of psychological response from the nurses like "the patient needs encouragement to perform an action" were fewer and had shorter hospital stay. In contrast to the positive response from the patients with nature view, people who were viewing the brick wall developed the need for more pain killer drugs as well as longer hospital stay.¹¹ This important study results could be applied in the case of the thesis were in some cases the seniors lack the ability of actually getting off the bed thus a view that faces nature could undoubtedly have beneficial outcomes on the seniors health physical as well as mental.

The lighting conditions can be very influential for a person's physical and mental state. In respect to that, Rixt F. Riemersma-van der Lek of the Netherlands Institute of Neuroscience along with her colleagues in 2008 performed a test in Holland at 12 retirement homes in order to prove the light importance and affects to a senior. The people had a daily interior light treatment of 1.000 lux and the other with 300 lux. The test had duration of 6 months. The results were shocking. The persons who were living in the brighter building where light was distributed more within the senior used spaces had showed 5% less cognitive decline in comparison with the seniors accommodating the darker, less well lighted building. In addition, within the brighter building depression also was reduced to 19%.¹²

Repositioning and Adaptation/ Eden Alternative Program

No matter the reason, moving away from your own house is a nerve-racking experience. Moving to a new living area due to ageing reasons is a difficult task that an elderly person is challenged to face when the move is been done from the lifelong house to the Senior Care Centre. Most common conditions that a person can face when admitted to the new living conditions of an Elderly Centre as Dr Thomas claimed to be the 3 plagues of the senior care facilities are loneliness, helplessness and boredom.¹³ These conditions are bound to occur when entering to a new situation, faced with the unfamiliar living environment, the need to start over among stranger. It is a moment where the elderly health can dramatically decline for the worst. If the person fails to shape any important friendships and to feel needed then the negative emotions of hopelessness, isolation, and rejection surface leading in some cases to tragic events. When the elderly feels that has absolutely no control on the environmental daily activities occurring around then the most possible reactions are self-enclosure, giving up and turning passive and depended. The senior have the need for a sense of motivation and hope that will keep them going, motivation for activity, for an easier adaptation to the new situation and determination that each day will be a new start.¹⁴

The most common emotions which are observed when an elderly person is ask to relocate at a new living environment are sense of loss, physical and cognitive limitations, lack of meaningful relationships and lack of opportunities to feel useful, all this leading to loneliness, depression, helplessness and boredom.¹⁵ In order to fight back the sense of helplessness as well as create the feeling of caring and in advance interest within a new living environment, an 8-week research by the University of Wisconsin- Milwaukee in 2008 took place at a long-term care facility in Canada. The study proved that the occupants, who were in the group assigned to care for a plant for watering and trimming, developed the sense of ownership and attachment reducing the sense of depression, increasing the sense of autonomy making the new environment to look much more familiar and friendly.¹⁶

By integrating nature within a long-term care environment can be one of the therapeutic design approaches proposed by cognitive psychotherapy and environmental enhancement architecture. Harvard Doctor William Thomas and his wife put a pilot project known as Eden Alternative¹⁷ to test at a pre-existing elderly centre named Tioga Nursing Facility in New York. The program was proposing a cure for loneliness in a humane environment as well as taking into consideration all the negative emotions established in the previous paragraphs. The solution proposed by Doctor Thomas was the introduction of living things within the living environment such as plants, pets, and kids. The seniors were able to care, feed and pet all the animals as well as water the plants, even play and interact with the kindergarten kids during some days of the week were intergenerational activities where taking place. The previous boring facility became a nursing home with life. The results were stunning there was a 25% decline of death rate, the patients were happier, they were living longer, and the medicine use dropped. The project had a huge success making an unfamiliar environment were

even the thought of a care centre considered unwanted to change and become a pleasant, happy, familiar place like a satisfied patient said "It is homier with plants and pets"¹⁸.

Nature has the ability to "control" humans. With its beauty and unique characteristics makes people to calm, relax, reduce stress and many other negative aspects of health while if it is manipulated correctly by architects can become part of the healing process for people with health issues as well as part of the psych, healing of depression, feeling of belonging and ownership. The enhancement of living conditions in a long-term care facility is essential for the users well being. Residents with less capability of movement and autonomous function are thought being in less privilege position from the rest of the inhabitants, thus a special care in their living environment but also for their adaptation and feeling of belonging is essential. In addition, it is necessary for the senior's residence health as well as for the people who look after them to be within an appropriate environment, which will promote health and socialization.

Sociopolis

Another very interesting project were socialization between various ages and social states is manifested was Sociopolis an urban proposal presented during 2003, by Guallart Architects and other ground breaking architects like MVRDV, No. MAD. The project was concentrated in the region of La Torre in Valencia, Spain and its aim was to promote a new type of urban development and living typologies. The key was to find a balance to the most important aspects of the 21st century living, being economy- affordable within good quality buildings as well as interior compositions and various social groups being able to co-exist within a harmonious environment. In addition, environmental sustainability by the use of the latest technologies for sufficient energy saving as well as conservation and restoration of the huerta¹⁹ was essential in order to maintain an important link with the city's history.

The development was oriented for the average middle-class population shaped by the groups at risk of social exclusion in an attempt to cover the need of cheap housing and socialization. This groups were young couples, for senior which in need for public care, or they are living alone, for people with disabilities or specific social group as well as foreigners. Part of the important issues for thought was this questions, "How do we avoid the total isolation of the individual in their environment, and achieve a greater social cohesion? How do we promote greater environmental quality, integrating nature into habitable environments? How do we use the new information technologies to build better and live better? How do we integrate new functions into the home? How do we foster a supportive habitat?"²⁰

Architects Vincent Guallart and Maria Diaz by proposing the Sharing Tower for Sociopolis were attempting to diminish and offer solutions to a number of issues raised during the study like socialization and mixing. By following a reference to the law of factor four²¹ the Share Tower stands on this code "in half the space or with half the resources we should achieve twice as many things in order to enhance the efficiency of our environment?"²² The mixture of multiple ages within a common residential environment or neighborhood is the best solution to avoid "age ghettos" and increase the feeling of all age acceptances within a society. Projects like the Sharing Tower plan is to encourage the residents to embrace a common habitat based on sharing, exchange and acceptance.

Elderly Care Centres in Cyprus

In Cyprus, not long ago the family bond used to be much different but a noticeable change occurred in a period of 20 years. The families used to live and grow all together, children, parents, grandparent even in some cases great grandparents. The care and respect for the older people was solid but the different mentality that came along with the fast society rhythms changed all that. When the parents arrive at a state where they are not able to perform their everyday needs, is common to hire at home a foreigner assistant, which aids the seniors at their home setting. Another more rare option is the accommodated of the elderly at his/her child's house or as considered for most people the last resolution the admission to a Senior Care Facility.

According to the KEMA research towards the attitude for staying in an old people's home only the 14% of the 100 seniors asked agreed that would accept this condition if there was no other option were 44% would not agree and find it cruel towards them.²³ Even though these results were part of a research completed in 1984, the results to this attitude have not changed today. Still people prefer to remain to their homes until late life rather than been relocated to a senior centre. The elderly in relation to their admission to a senior centre is

worrying if their families will forget them, if they will lose their everyday habits and neighbourhood friends along with their autonomy and familiar environment. At the same time, they worry in what kind of condition their new home will be and if the care that will have will be appropriate. The conditions of senior living at both, state as well as private care centres varies from well maintained to poor almost inhumane conditions. The state owns 7 in total elderly centres, 2 are located in Nicosia, The House for Elderly and Disable in Anthoupoli and in Latsia, were the rest are private sectors. The typologies of the private centres most frequently is a previous residential family houses which was altered and refurbished. Due to this alternations of the structure from house to a multiple person living even though the intensions might be the reminded of homier environment the conditions often lack this house warmth and become boring and passive setting. Although some of the buildings are located within neighbourhoods the seniors do not seem to interact with the rest of the neighbourhood residents and city fabric rather they most often stay put at the locations placed by the personnel all day long lacking the empowerment and the will to act and interact. As the year passes the population of senior citizens, 65+ registered by the Cyprus Demographic Reports from 2005 to 2008 raise from 12.04% to 12.69%.²⁴

The state according to the Ministry of Work and Social Services of Cyprus offers some locations and special programs for the seniors in the effort to cover some unavoidable needs of this population portion. These programs are:

1. Home Care: is the type of system were care personnel from the government or from a private organization, visits the seniors' house, and offers general assisting
2. Day Care Program: offers the ability to the senior to visit and use the Senior Centers governmental as well as private units during the day
3. Institutional Care: state senior institute were accommodation and living care is offered
4. Adults Centres: areas designed for the seniors for the pleasant passage of the day offering food, laundry, occupation, and entertainment house, and offers general assisting.²⁵

Proposal to Cyprus, a new type of Senior Care Development

This part of the paper is devoted specifically on the Cyprus issue of Senior Care development private and governmental proposing a possible solution subtracted and influenced by the various examples observed worldwide. Even though an elderly centre may not be the most desired living environment that a senior may want in some cases is the only solution when the disabilities of the elderly live no other choice. By using, interview examples by RUBSI as well as KEMA towards the senior population in Cyprus the needs and the requirements are clear being on them the development of prober senior centres.

Figure 1. General view of the design proposal

STRATEGIES	CHARACTERISTICS	SOCIAL RELATIONS
<p>site location</p> <p>importance for success the location of the care complex to be a busy frequently used area by multiple ages within the city fabric but most importantly where nature will be also equally existing.</p>	<p>*highly used location by multiple-ages *within the city *within nature</p>	
<p>cohabitation</p> <p>concept of sharing through living spaces as well as common activity locations. Cohabitation of various ages within the same unit. Interaction and care increase.</p>	<p>*sharing accommodation and spaces *save money *ex-change of skills *mutual care</p>	
<p>paths/interactions</p> <p>various facilities and will be incorporated in the complex to attract the public and the dwellers where paths will turn to meeting points and connect the rest of the site with the development.</p>	<p>*site pathways becoming part of the complex *various types of textures/speeds *paths become social spaces of interaction</p>	
<p>eden alternative program</p> <p>use the program to turn senior living into residence of life by incorporating living subjects like plantation, animals, kids turning the space more familiar and friendly diminishing loneliness, isolation, helplessness.</p>	<p>*socialization by petting *caring development by gardening *hommier environment by taking part at household activities *kids interaction_development of new "family bonds"</p>	
<p>empowerment programs</p> <p>various programs like yoga, dancing, choir, arts and crafts, movie nights etc will be incorporated within the complex empowering socialization but also activity between seniors with the public, senior with multiple ages as well as empowers the positive opinion of the elderly developments in Cyprus.</p>	<p>*socialization programs for the public and the residents *multigeneration activities *creation of positive opinion about the elderly developments</p>	
<p>population recycling</p> <p>the ability to have intern students as well as awareness programs where specific people can inhabit the complex for an amount of time learning about the beneficial factors of the proposal and spreading the knowledge.</p>	<p>*boundary softening *educational/experiential program</p>	

Figure 2. Strategies, Characteristics and Social Relations

By having as a base the Sharing Tower as well as the Eden Alternative Program a proposal of a multigenerational neighbourhood development arises explaining in detail what could offer to the users. The aim is not to provide an individual structure rather offer a pilot project that aims to reverse the living isolation faced by the seniors when entering a common elderly centre, smooth the elderly transition and adaptation to the new living settings as well as encourage a multi-aging socialization and age acceptance. With the use of multiple strategies of economy sharing, user's socialization possibilities as well as greater public attraction within the same complex will all be part of a healing environmental approach developed in an architectural manner exploring the maximum positive effects that a build or non-build community can offer.

RUBSI program (Research Unit in Behavior & Social Issues) issued a research²⁶ during 2007 and its outcomes stated clearly the need for the formation of an upgraded development dedicated to the senior population but it is my belief that the creation of a structure were only seniors will be accommodated will not succeed to prevent social exclusion, therefore a creation of a new model of multigenerational accommodation weaved into a social network along with the therapeutic design techniques and the application of the Eden Alternative program is proposed. Through this development, the aim is to reverse the living isolation faced by the seniors when entering a common elderly centre, smooth the elderly transition and ease the adaptation to a new living setting as well as encourage a multi-aging socialization and age acceptance.

Why not shape a pilot project within the Cypriot community taking into consideration the examples of socialization seen in Eden Alternative program and in the Sharing Tower project twisting those techniques in order to fit within the Cypriot mentality as well as community. Therefore a complex were share living could also combine a variety of people within the same environment were socialization would start due to common space use and thus an unavoidable interaction. The promotion of a sharing economy, could be considered as one strong link between people and acceptance since it could also offer minimum spent in renting as well as other services a crucial point if we take into consideration the economical crisis that all the countries are facing. "So why not to share in order to save more?"

Figure 3. View of the design proposal. Common areas

The people forming this complex are one of the most important elements for the proposals success. By having in mind the need for multiple ages within the same location as well as the economical factor that will keep this people together the group of people for the Cyprus proposal considered to be more appropriate are, seniors who need intensive care, and minor care, single parents with children, university students and resent university graduates who are trying to build their lives. The groups selected are people who will need accommodation with the less money spent but equally good condition of living. All the groups for their reasons need to spent less money, the seniors might have small pension, and the single parent might not have much to spend and need to work all day while the child must be looked after when she/he is away. The university students and the recent graduate's need an affordable living accommodation that will allow them to save some of their money thus, each person will accept to live in a share community because of the amount of money, that can save and the mutual help, which can share between those people.

By mixing ages with common living conditions, an unavoidable caring community is bound to evolve. The concept of sharing along with the idea of various different ages users a multi-generational socialization will emerge. In order to empower and maintain socialization between the residents a strategy of skill exchange between the residents could be an extra point. This exchange will be about people contributing to the common living environment or by offering services between them. For example when the single parent is out for work until late one of the senior residents could look after the child with salary or not, the independent senior could do the light shopping at the bakery by foot were one of the younger people could do the heavy shopping by car. The garden could be maintained by some people were others who will not have enough time could trade garden maintenance with laundry or food or other chords. Senior people with no car instead of using a taxi could ask from one of the persons, which own a car, to car pool with less money or free. The people living within the unit could also use their own lifelong skills whenever are considered necessary like when a plumber or a technician will be needed. Also everyday functions of cooking, ironing, laundry and cleaning could be part of the apartments combination were people from various apartments could start not only sharing between the same unit as well as with the rest for more economical sustainability. The support of seniors and not only, to continue doing activities, which were part of their everyday life, is essential to give a sense of control to their daily activities avoiding the negative reaction of self-enclosure, give up and passive, depended reaction, emotions which strongly emerge after relocation.

Figure 4. View of the design proposal. Pathways and living quarters

Transition from one's home to a new living setting is hard not only for seniors as well as for any person who needs to re-adjust to new conditions of living. Seniors tend to develop physical and cognitive limitations, facing difficulties to develop meaningful relationships as well as the opportunities of them feel useful are limited. Due to these facts, the strategies aim to promote sense of ownership and belonging as well as familiarity and activities that a person was doing at home. The persons will be able to bring furniture's from their homes, which feel attached with and decorate their rooms as they want and feel more comfortable. In addition, the development of care and sense of being needed by other living things will be more empowered when the senior start caring for animals and plantation like at home an example successfully used by Doctor William Thomas and the Eden Alternative program with impressive results.²⁷

The study at the University of Wisconsin- Milwaukee²⁸ proved the occupants, who were assigned to care for a plant for watering and trimming, developed the sense of ownership and attachment reducing the sense of depression, creating a sense of autonomy making the new environment to look much more familiar and friendly. An important part for this caring treatment could also be kids who will enhance even more the intergenerational program were in some days of the week the kids and seniors will spend common time interacting with each other, the elderly gaining a new grandchild and the child a new grandparent. By offering a motivation for action like gardening, exercise and walking as well as social activities like coffee gatherings, singing competitions, card and tavli games, cooking, arts and crafts, knitting and various other everyday actions can help the seniors moral that they did not come to the senior centre to die. By using the KEMA research for the old age in Cyprus many of the activities that the seniors were considered to be part of their daily entertainment are the once mentioned above plus reading and resting²⁹. By applying all this strategies, the 3 plagues of the seniors at the elderly care facilities as Dr Thomas correctly titled loneliness, helplessness and boredom as well as hopelessness, isolation and rejection are being defeated. All the elderly needs are an environment physical and mental which will bust a sense of motivation and hope that will keep them going. The site selection is one of the most important factors, which has the power to influence the building's design and in general, the correct projects development. As stated at the second part the environment that one is constantly exposed has the power to affect the person's health. In consequence, the site selection for the development of the new model of neighbourhood is an important key to the success of the program.

Figure 5. View of the design proposal. Pathways

The importance of having constant public use of the site is essential since physical disability is one of the reasons that seniors are forced to lose their socialization skills, therefore the public should come to them. As a result the proposed building must be shaped as part of the landscape subtracting the therapeutic role of nature by also taking under consideration the characteristics of the location and how is currently used by the users. By combining the previous familiar site conditions weaved within the new neighbourhood complex, the public site users will continue their everyday activities but this time mingling also with the neighbourhood residents through movement, transitions, as well as common activities offer also for the greater public. These three ways of building manipulation also by the site visitors could be one strong action were the society boundaries between seniors and other ages are softened along with the multigenerational living.

Promoting a social boundary softening various services are included within the complex. The neighbourhood can include a kindergarten as part of the intergenerational program as well as a Community Hub the main activity space that will spatially connect the general city public with the new development. It will be the most active location where the public and the residents will use for everyday social activities like card games, coffee gathering, dancing or even movie night. The formation of the space will offer the easy space alteration and space expansion indoors as well as outwards according to activities need enable socialization and constant environmental interest. Volunteers will be welcome to assist with the intensive care unit and various event preparations and finally the daily side users will be able to rest at the cafe and dinner as well as use the buildings spaces as part of their walk.

The whole development is thought to be as a healthy sustainable environmental where special elderly services and precise networks and facilities can be incorporated shaping an integrated area of living and leisure for equal citizens. The whole development will offer a different point of view reconsidering the senior living conditions which are currently surrounding us within the Cypriot community and promote awareness of other possible solutions which are thriving abroad with their techniques posing the question "Why we do not act and improve the seniors living conditions at care centres, isn't there a possibility of us ending up in one of those at some point of our life?"

Figure 6. view of the design proposal-courtyard

Figure 7. Roof Plan of the building proposal and views

Conclusion

The aim of the entire paper is to bring awareness about the new ideas of senior centres to Cyprus. The project as a whole is directed to the development of a new sustainable community where various age groups come together and start sharing living spaces as well as daily activities within the same neighbourhood. Thus, by incorporating the various researches of therapeutic environmental test results and the positive outcomes from the case studies, the proposed developments goal is to reverse negative mentality towards the senior homes and bring multiple social and age groups together in an attempt to minimize the ageing racism as well as economical expenses through a cohabitated, socializing environment.

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- ²⁷ Goodman, "The Eden Alternative,"2007.
- ²⁸ Kiyota , *People-Nature Interactions*, 1-7.
- ²⁹ KEMA, *Research for the Old Age in Cyprus*, 59.